

ISic3110

Funerary inscription for Philokles

Language

Type

Material

Object

Editor

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Autopsy

2017-03-20

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di
Catania, inventory 929

Physical Description

and A rough slab of irregular shape, damaged upper right
along the lower edge. The rear is rough in finish.

Dimensions

Height 19.5 cm

Width 30 cm

Depth 5.5-5.7 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-3: 32-54 mm

Interlineation

Not measured: mm

Text

1. Φιλοκλή

2. χρηστὲ

3. χάρε

Apparatus

Translation (en)

Farewell worthy Philokles!

Translation (it)

Addio, degno Filocle!

Commentary

Although the stone is damaged, it seems likely that the text is complete. The formula is a typical one of Greek funerary inscriptions, particularly of the later Hellenistic and early Imperial period, and addresses the deceased directly (compare the bilingual example no.22). The name Philokles is a common one, found elsewhere in Sicily (e.g. at Akrai and Monte San Fratello = ancient Apollonia (ISic1187)). The relatively poor quality of the epitaph and the material suggest that this tombstone probably comes from the rural hinterland of Catania, and not from the city itself.

The usual form of the vocative would be Φιλοκλεῖς, but parallels can be found for the form in this inscription, such as in a second-century BC example from Delos, in M.T. Couilloud, *Les monuments funéraires de Rhénée* (Exploration archéologique de Délos ; fasc. 30), Paris, Dépositaire Diffusion de Boccard (1974), no.16: Φιλοκλή Θεοδότου Δήλιε χρηστὲ χαῖρε.

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Bibliography

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